

The Post Buckling Behaviour of Composite Panels

by

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Introduction

The last two decades have seen the introduction of a number of high strength and high modulus fibres and whiskers. This has permitted the fabrication of composites with highly anisotropic properties and in particular the fabrication of orthotropic panels using uni-directional reinforcement. As composites become increasingly used for structural applications, an accurate assessment of their load carrying potential is essential. One area of particular interest is their ability to carry in plane loads. Where one or other of the composite constituents has a low modulus of elasticity, instability becomes a serious problem. If however this low modulus is combined with a high strength the possibility of a large post buckling range is enhanced. This paper examines the post buckling behaviour of plates in this category.

The ability of plates to carry loads beyond the critical stage when buckling is initiated, has been known for decades. With loads beyond the critical value the plate remains in stable equilibrium. There is however a development of out of plane deflections, a change in the stress pattern and an effective decrease in the load carrying efficiency of the panel.

The post buckling behaviour of orthotropic plates has received some though not extensive cover in the literature. Recently Prabhakara and Chia (1) and (2) have published some work on such plates, simply supported on all edges and subjected to a constant stress across the plate after buckling. They also give some references to earlier work in this field. The present work differs from the above in two main respects. It is not limited to simple supports

on the unloaded edges, these edges being considered to be elastically restrained, and the loaded edges are assumed to have a constant in plane displacement. This would appear to be nearer the practical case in most applications. In addition a completely different theoretical approach is adopted.

The general method of analysis in the present case is essentially that first used by Marguerre (3) and more recently by Rhodes and Harvey (4) who applied it to isotropic plates. It consists essentially of choosing a suitable expression for the deflected form of the buckled plate and using the large deflection equation to obtain the corresponding stress system. Considering the strain energy in the buckled plate system the theorem of minimum total potential energy is then used to obtain the values of the coefficients in the deflection series and hence the final deflected form. The present work is an extension of the above isotropic analysis to orthotropic plates, which are becoming increasingly important in the context of the growing technology of composite materials.

Theoretical Analysis

The analysis is based on the consideration of the specially orthotropic plate subjected to in plane loading in the x-direction as indicated in Fig.1. The x-direction indicates the major stiffness axis for the plate. Throughout, the subscripts 1 and 2 will correspond to the x and y axes respectively. The constitutive relationship for the plate is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tau_x \\ \tau_y \\ \tau_{2y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where the components of the compliance matrix, S, are given by

$$S_{11} = 1/E_{11} ; \quad S_{12} = -\nu_{12}/E_{11} = -\nu_{21}/E_{22} ;$$

$$S_{22} = 1/E_{22} ; \quad S_{66} = 1/C_{12}$$

Large Deflection Equations

The large deflection equations governing the post buckling behaviour of homogeneous orthotropic plates are an extension of the well known von Karman equations for thin isotropic plates of uniform thickness. The development of these equations is given by Timoshenko (5) and the extension for orthotropic analysis by Lekhnitskii (6). Using the non linear relationships for mid surface strains in terms of deflection:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \\ \epsilon_y &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

together with (1) an equation can be obtained linking the stress function F and deflections w . This equation is thus based on compatibility considerations and the constitutive relations and is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{E_{22}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \right) \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{1}{E_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4} \\ = \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

The stress function F is such that the mid surface stresses in the plate are defined by

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} ; \quad \sigma_y = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} ; \quad \tau_{xy} = - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (4)$$

Usually a second non linear large deflection equation is obtained from equilibrium considerations again involving both the stress function F and deflection w . This is then used together with (3) to obtain a solution for F and w , an assumed form having been chosen for both these functions.

In the present work, however, a suitable expression for the deflection function w alone is chosen containing a number of independent parameters consistent with the boundary conditions. Equation (3) is then used to solve for the stress function F in terms of w exactly. Having obtained an expression for the strain energy of the buckled plate system the above functions are then inserted into this equation. The unknown parameters in the deflection function are then determined so that the total potential energy computed on the basis of the approximate displacements is a minimum. This latter approach is essentially the Rayleigh-Ritz method.

Boundary Conditions

The plate is considered to be simply supported on its loaded ends while the unloaded edges are elastically restrained against rotation to an equal or unequal degree. Hence the following conditions

must be satisfied on edges $y = 0$ and $y = b$.

$$w = 0$$

$$-D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \nu_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) / \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = \text{elastic constant, } \alpha \quad (5)$$

Noting that $\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}$ is zero along these edges if $w = 0$ these equations can be simplified to

$$w = 0$$

$$-D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) / \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = \alpha \quad (6)$$

The membrane boundary conditions are considered as follows. On the loaded ends the shear stress is zero and the in plane displacement is assumed constant across the plate. To examine the behaviour of the plate after buckling this displacement is prescribed. Hence

$$\tilde{\tau}_{xy} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad x = -a/2 \quad \text{and} \quad x = +a/2$$

$$u = \text{constant across plate} \quad (7)$$

On the unloaded edges both the direct stress and shear stress are assumed to be zero. This means that the plate is free to wave in the plane of the plate. Hence when $y = 0$ and $y = b$

$$\tilde{\tau}_{xy} = 0 \quad ; \quad \sigma_y = 0 \quad (8)$$

Deflection Function

For the plate shown in Fig.1 the deflections vary sinusoidally in the x direction at loads in the region of that to cause buckling. The expression for w can thus be taken in the form

$$w = Y(y) \cos \frac{\pi x}{e} \quad (9)$$

where e is a measure of the buckle half wave length in the x direction. The deflections across the plate $Y(y)$ are taken in a manner similar to that used by Rhodes and Harvey (4), i.e. in the form of a series

$$Y = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n Y_n \quad (10)$$

The coefficient A_n by which each function Y_n is multiplied governs the magnitude of the deflections occurring in the plate.

The functions Y_n are chosen as algebraic functions of the form

$$Y_n = \left[(y/b) + d_{1n}(y/b)^2 + d_{2n}(y/b)^{a_n} + d_{3n}(y/b)^{b_n} \right] \quad (11)$$

where a_n and b_n are arbitrary integers which are given different values for different values of n and d_{1n} , d_{2n} and d_{3n} are used to satisfy the flexural boundary conditions at the plate edges.

Hence the boundary conditions (6) can now be re-written as

$$Y_n = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{Y_n''}{Y_n'} = \frac{\alpha}{D_{22}} = \frac{R}{b} \quad (13)$$

R is the coefficient of restraint at the plate edges given by $b\alpha/D_{22}$ and may have different values at either edge. For generality the value on the edge $y = 0$ is called R_0 and that on edge $y = b$ is called R_b . For positive restraint on rotation R_0 is positive and R_b is negative. Note that α , the rotational stiffness of the restraining medium would thus be given by $R D_{22}/b$.

By substituting for Y_n in equations (12) and (13) it can be shown that the boundary conditions are satisfied if

$$d_{1n} = \frac{R_0}{2}$$

$$d_{2n} = -1 - d_{1n} - d_{3n} \quad (14)$$

$$d_{3n} = \frac{R_b + R_0 R_b - R_0 - a_n R_b \left(1 + \frac{R_0}{2}\right) + a_n (a_n - 1) \left(1 + \frac{R_0}{2}\right)}{b_n (b_n - 1) - a_n (a_n - 1) - R_b (b_n - a_n)}$$

The deflection function Y_n is thus completely specified. Changes in the function for different n values is obtained by specifying the indices a_n and b_n .

Stress Function

The stress function F can now be obtained in terms of w by substituting for w from equation (9) into equation (3). On re-arranging the following is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \right) \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{1}{E_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4} \\ & = \frac{\pi^2}{2c^2 b^2} \left[(Y Y'' + (Y')^2) + (Y Y'' - (Y')^2) \cos \frac{2\pi x}{cb} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

A solution for F can thus be obtained in the form

$$F = F_1(y) + F_2(y) \cdot \cos \frac{2\pi x}{2b} \quad (16)$$

Substituting from (16) into (15) and rearranging shows that F_1 and F_2 can be obtained from

$$\frac{1}{E_{11}} \cdot F_1^{IV} = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2 b^2} \left[\gamma \gamma'' + (\gamma')^2 \right] \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{1}{E_{11}} F_2^{IV} - \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^2 \cdot H \cdot F_2'' + \frac{1}{E_{22}} F_2 \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^4 = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2 b^2} \left[\gamma \gamma'' - (\gamma')^2 \right] \quad (18)$$

where

$$H = \frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}}$$

Thus F_1 is independent of x and hence constant along the length of the 1 plate. While F_1 can not therefore give a stress in the y direction, it does give a stress in the x direction which is found by integrating (17) twice. This gives

$$F_1'' = \frac{E_1 \pi^2}{2e^2 b^2} \frac{\gamma^2}{2} + B y + C \quad (19)$$

where B and C are constants and found from the membrane boundary conditions on the loaded ends.

To obtain an expression for F_2 equation (10) is used. Substituting in (18) gives

$$\frac{1}{E_{11}} F_2^{IV} - H \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^2 F_2'' + \frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^4 F_2 = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2 b^2} \left[\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N A_n A_m (\gamma_n \gamma_m'' - \gamma_n' \gamma_m') \right] \quad (20)$$

If γ_n is assumed to take the general algebraic form

$$\gamma_n = \sum_{p=1}^r C_{pn} \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^p \quad (21)$$

substituting in equation (20) and manipulating gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{E_{11}} F_2^{IV} - H \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^2 F_2'' + \frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^4 F_2 \\ = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2 b^4} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N A_n A_m \sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} B_{smn} \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^s \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$B_{s,mn} = \sum_{q=1}^r C_{(s+2-q),m} C_{q,m} [q(q-1) - q(s+2-q)] \quad (23)$$

and $s = p + q - 2$ (24)

A solution for F_2 can be found by putting F_2 in the form

$$F_2 = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2 b^4} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N A_n A_m \phi_{mn}(y) \quad (25)$$

Substituting in equation (22) gives

$$\frac{1}{E_{11}} \phi_{mn}^{(4)} - H \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 \phi_{mn}^{(2)} + \frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^4 \phi_{mn} = \sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} B_{s,mn} \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^s \quad (26)$$

If now ϕ_{mn} is assumed to take the form

$$\phi_{mn} = \sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} L_{s,mn} \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^s \quad (27)$$

substituting in equation (26) and equating coefficients from each term in turn gives

$$\begin{aligned} L_{s,mn} = & \frac{B_{s,mn}}{\frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^4} + \frac{H(s+1)(s+2)}{\frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 b^2} L_{(s+2),mn} \\ & - \frac{\frac{1}{E_{11}} (s+1)(s+2)(s+3)(s+4)}{\frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^4 b^4} L_{(s+4),mn} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

It is clear that the evaluation of L must be made from $S = 2(r - 1)$ since for all values of $S > 2(r - 1)$, $L_{s,mn}$ must be zero and

$L_{(s+2),mn}$ and $L_{(s+4),mn}$ must be known before $L_{s,mn}$ can be evaluated.

Equation (28) thus gives the particular integral solution for equation (26). To obtain a complete solution for ϕ the complementary function solution must be added to this. There are three possible solutions to the homogeneous equation:

$$\phi_{mn}^{iv} - \bar{E}_{11} H \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^2 \phi_{mn}^{ii} + \frac{\bar{E}_{11}}{\bar{E}_{22}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^4 \phi_{mn} = 0 \quad (29)$$

consistent with the values of E_1 , E_2 and H .

1. If $E_1^2 H^2 > 4 \frac{E_1}{E_2}$ then all roots are real
2. If $E_1^2 H^2 = 4 \frac{E_1}{E_2}$ then the roots are equal. This is the isotropic case
3. If $E_1^2 H^2 < 4 \frac{E_1}{E_2}$ then all roots are complex

In this paper only the first of these conditions are dealt with since this is consistent with the class of materials considered. The solution to equation (29) is thus

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{mn} = & C_{1mn} \cosh k_1 y + C_{2mn} \sinh k_1 y \\ & + C_{3mn} \cosh k_2 y + C_{4mn} \sinh k_2 y \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where $k_1 = \left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \left(\bar{E}_{11} H + \sqrt{(\bar{E}_{11}^2 H^2 - 4 \frac{\bar{E}_{11}}{\bar{E}_{22}})} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (31)

and $k_2 = \left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{2b} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \left(\bar{E}_{11} H - \sqrt{(\bar{E}_{11}^2 H^2 - 4 \frac{\bar{E}_{11}}{\bar{E}_{22}})} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$

The complete solution for ϕ_{mn} is thus

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{mn} = & \sum_{s=0}^{2l-1} L_{s,mn} \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^s + C_{1mn} \cosh k_1 y + C_{2mn} \sinh k_1 y \\ & + C_{3mn} \cosh k_2 y + C_{4mn} \sinh k_2 y \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The values of the constants C_{1mn} etc. can be obtained by considering the boundary conditions on the plate edges. It can be shown that equation (8) is satisfied if on the edges $y = 0$ and $y = b$

$$\phi_{mn} = 0 \quad ; \quad \phi_{mn}^i = 0 \quad (33)$$

The constants are thus found to be

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{1mn} &= -T_6 / T_5 \\
 C_{2mn} &= \frac{T_2 - C_{1mn} T_3}{T_4} \\
 C_{3mn} &= -L_{cmn} - C_{1mn} \\
 C_{4mn} &= \frac{-L_{1mn}(1/b) - k_1 C_{2mn}}{k_2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{2mn} &= \frac{L_{1mn}(\frac{1}{b})}{k_2} \sinh k_2 b + L_{cmn} \cosh k_2 b - \sum L_{5mn} \\
 T_3 &= \cosh k_1 b - \cosh k_2 b \\
 T_4 &= \sinh k_1 b - \frac{k_1}{k_2} \sinh k_2 b \\
 T_{5mn} &= \sum L_{5mn} \left[\frac{1}{b} + k_1 \frac{T_2}{T_4} \cosh k_1 b - k_2 L_{cmn} \sinh k_2 b \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left[L_1 \frac{1}{b} + k_1 \frac{T_2}{T_4} \right] \cosh k_2 b \right] \\
 T_5 &= k_1 \sinh k_1 b - k_1 \frac{T_3}{T_4} \cosh k_1 b - k_2 \sinh k_2 b + k_1 \frac{T_3}{T_4} \cosh k_2 b
 \end{aligned}$$

The stress function F has thus been completely determined in terms of the deflection function. The constants in equation (19) can now be found by applying the boundary conditions, equation (7), for the loaded ends of the plate and by examining the prescribed end displacement system. Noting that

$$\mu = \int_{-c/2}^{c/2} \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} - \nu_{12} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] dx \tag{35}$$

and substituting for F and w and integrating (terms in F_2 integrate to zero because of the periodicity of F_2) the following equation for F_1'' is obtained

$$F_1'' = -\frac{\mu E_{11}}{\alpha} + \frac{E_{11} \tau^2}{4e^2 b^2} y^2 \tag{36}$$

Substituting from equation (19) gives

$$-\mu = \frac{\alpha}{E_{11}} (By + C) \tag{37}$$

To have a uniform end displacement system across the plate B is therefore zero and the magnitude of the end displacement is then specified by C.

$$C = - \frac{u E_{11}}{a} \quad (38)$$

which is the stress required to compress the unbuckled plate by an amount u .

The zero shear stress condition at the loaded ends is automatically satisfied.

Energy Formulations

The strain energy in the buckled plate in the present case is made up of three parts - the potential energy of deformation, the membrane stretch energy and the energy from the rotational restraint at the boundaries. These in turn are given by

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \int_0^b \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 2 D_{11} \nu_{21} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + 4 D_{33} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right] dx dy \quad (39)$$

$$V_2 = \frac{k}{2} \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \int_0^b \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 - \frac{2 \nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{1}{G_{12}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \right] dx dy \quad (40)$$

$$V_3 = - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \left[D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \nu_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) \right]_{y=0}^{y=b} dx \quad (41)$$

The total strain energy is thus given by

$$V = V_1 + V_2 + V_3 \quad (42)$$

Substituting for w and F in equation (42) and integrating with respect to x gives

$$V = \frac{a}{4} \sum_n \sum_m A_n A_m \left\{ \int_0^b \left[D_{22} Y_n'' Y_m'' + \left(\frac{\pi^2}{2^2 b^2} \right)^2 D_{11} Y_n Y_m - \frac{2 \pi^2}{2^2 b^2} D_{11} \nu_{21} Y_n Y_m'' + 4 D_{33} \frac{\pi^2}{2^2 b^2} Y_n' Y_m' - \frac{k E_{11} \pi^2}{a 2^2 b^2} u Y_n Y_n \right] dy + D_{22} \left[Y_n'' Y_m' \right]_{y=0}^{y=b} \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\alpha k}{4} \left[\frac{\pi^4}{E_c^4 b^4} \sum \sum \sum \sum A_n A_m A_p A_q \left\{ \int_c^b [\bar{E}_{11} \gamma_n \gamma_m \gamma_p \gamma_q \right. \right. \quad (43) \\
& \quad + \frac{2}{b^4} \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}} \Phi_{mn}'' \Phi_{pq}'' + \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 \left[\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \Phi_{mn}'' \Phi_{pq} + \Phi_{mn}' \Phi_{pq}' \frac{1}{G_{12}} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 \frac{1}{E_{22}} \Phi_{mn} \Phi_{pq} \right] \right] \right\} + \int_c^b \frac{2\alpha^2 \bar{E}_{11}}{\alpha^2} dy \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The magnitude of the coefficients A_n can now be obtained by minimising the strain energy. Differentiating V with respect to each coefficient in turn gives a series of simultaneous cubic equations from which the values of A_n can be obtained. It is clear that the computation becomes significant as the number of terms are increased. An accurate estimate of the deflected form at buckling can be obtained by considering only the second powers of A_n in equation (43) since as the deflection magnitudes approach zero, the second powers of A_n are relatively much greater than the fourth powers.

Thus by eliminating all terms in equation (43) with A_n to the fourth power and differentiating with respect to A_n a series of linear simultaneous equations are obtained from which the value of u to cause buckling can be found. The relative values of A_n can also be obtained. The absolute values, however, are indeterminate from the buckling solution. Knowing the relative values the deflection function can be re-written as, say,

$$w = A_1 \left[\gamma_1 + \frac{A_2}{A_1} \gamma_2 + \frac{A_3}{A_1} \gamma_3 + \frac{A_4}{A_1} \gamma_4 + \dots \right] \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb}$$

which can be re-defined as

$$w = \bar{A} \bar{\gamma} \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (44)$$

This is an accurate description of the first buckling mode, i.e. the deflected form of the plate at buckling. The value for $\bar{\gamma}$ corresponding to \bar{A} can be obtained as shown previously and substituting in equation (43) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
V = \frac{\alpha}{4} \bar{A}^2 \left\{ \int_c^b \left[D_{22} (\bar{\gamma}'')^2 + \left(\frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} \right)^2 D_{11} \bar{\gamma}^2 - \frac{2\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} D_{11} \nu_{21} \bar{\gamma} \bar{\gamma}'' \right. \right. \\
\left. \left. + 4 D_{33} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} \bar{\gamma} \bar{\gamma}' - \frac{k E_{11} \pi^2}{\alpha e^2 b^2} u (\bar{\gamma})^2 \right] dy + D_{22} [\bar{\gamma}'' \bar{\gamma}']_{y=0}^{y=b} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{\alpha k}{4} \left[\frac{\pi^4}{E_0 e^4 b^4} \bar{A}^4 \left\{ \int_c^b [E_{11} (\bar{\gamma})^4 + \frac{2}{b^4} \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}} (\bar{\phi}''')^2 + \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 \left[\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \bar{\phi}'' \bar{\phi} \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. \left. + (\bar{\phi}')^2 \frac{1}{C_{12}} + \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 \frac{1}{E_{22}} (\bar{\phi})^2 \right] \right] \right\} + \int_c^b \frac{2 \alpha^2 E_{11}}{e^2} dy \right. \\
 & \left. \right] \quad (45)
 \end{aligned}$$

Differentiating V with respect to \bar{A} and setting derivative equal to zero gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{A} = & \left. \begin{aligned} & \frac{k E_{11}}{\alpha} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} \alpha \int_c^b (\bar{\gamma})^2 dy - \left\{ \int_c^b [D_{22} (\bar{\gamma}'')^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} D_{11} \bar{\gamma}^2 \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{2\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} D_{11} \nu_{21} \bar{\gamma} \bar{\gamma}'' + 4 D_{33} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} (\bar{\gamma}')^2 \right] dy + D_{22} [\bar{\gamma}'' \bar{\gamma}']_{y=c}^{y=b} \right\} \\ & \frac{k \pi^4}{4 e^4 b^4} \int_c^b \left[E_{11} \bar{\gamma}^4 + \frac{2}{b^4} \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}} (\bar{\phi}''')^2 + \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb} \right)^2 \left[\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \bar{\phi}'' \bar{\phi} \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left. \left. + (\bar{\phi}')^2 \frac{1}{C_{12}} + \frac{2\pi}{eb} \frac{1}{E_{22}} (\bar{\phi})^2 \right] \right] \right] dy \right. \\ & \left. \right] \quad (46)
 \end{aligned}
 \end{aligned}$$

The value of \bar{A} can thus be obtained for any prescribed end displacement system u which is greater than u_{cr} (if $u < u_{cr}$ then \bar{A} is imaginary). Knowing \bar{A} the stresses and deflections in the plate can be evaluated. In particular the post buckling stiffness of the plate can be obtained from a consideration of the load in the plate

$$P = k \int_c^b \sigma_x dx = k \int_c^b \left(\bar{\sigma}_1'' + \bar{\sigma}_2'' \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \right) dx \quad (47)$$

Substituting gives

$$P = \frac{k E_0 b}{\alpha} u - \frac{k E_0 \pi^2}{4 e^2 b^2} \bar{A} \int_c^b \bar{\gamma}^2 dy \quad (48)$$

In the usual way the pre-buckling stiffness is found by setting \bar{A} equal to zero and differentiating with respect to u

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial u} = \frac{k E_0 b}{\alpha} \quad (49)$$

The post buckling stiffness can be obtained from equation (48) remembering that A is now a function of u . Substituting for \bar{A} from equation (46) and differentiating with respect to u gives the required value. The ratio of post buckling stiffness to pre buckling stiffness can thus be obtained as

$$\frac{E^*}{E} = 1 - \frac{\frac{E_{11}}{b} \left[\int_c^b (\bar{\gamma})^2 dy \right]^2}{\int_c^b \left\{ E_{11} (\bar{\gamma})^4 + \frac{2}{b^4} \left[\frac{(\bar{\Phi}''')^2}{E_{11}} + \frac{4\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} \left(\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} (\bar{\Phi}''') \bar{\Phi} + (\bar{\Phi}')^2 \frac{1}{G_{12}} + \frac{4\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} \frac{1}{E_{22}} \bar{\Phi}^2 \right) \right] \right\} dy} \quad (50)$$

To obtain the membrane stresses at any position along the length of the plate the effect of F_2 can be added to equation (48) giving

$$\sigma_x^m = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} = -\frac{u E_{11}}{a} + \frac{E_{11} \pi^2}{4e^2 b^2} \bar{A}^{-2} \bar{\gamma}^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2 b^2} \bar{A}^{-2} \bar{\Phi}'' \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \quad (51)$$

The bending stresses can be found in the usual way giving

$$\sigma_x^b = \frac{6D_{11}}{e^2} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} \bar{A} \bar{\gamma} - \nu_{21} \bar{A} \bar{\gamma}'' \right) \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (52)$$

Theoretical Results and Discussion

The above analysis has been applied in particular to glass reinforced plastic plates, since the initial objective in introducing this research programme was to investigate the possible structural exploitation of this class of composite. In addition, some experimental work with GRP plates has been completed and correlation with the results will be indicated. The analysis, however, can obviously be applied to other composites and some examples of this will be given. Typical values of the elastic constants for the plates used by the author are $E_{11} = 30 \text{ GN/m}^2$, $E_{22} = 6 \text{ GN/m}^2$, $G_{12} = 2 \text{ GN/m}^2$ and $\nu_{12} = 0.3$.

Unless otherwise stated, results shown are for these basic values (referred to as Plate 1 in the Figs.).

Non dimensional load-end displacement curves are shown in Fig.2 for various values of positive rotational restraint on the edges.

The post buckling stiffness varies from 0.35 for the simply supported case ($R = 0$) to around a maximum value of 0.48. The curves follow the expected trend.

The effect of the rotational restraint on the unloaded edges on the post buckling stiffness and the buckling load is shown in Fig.3. The buckling load coefficient K is defined in a manner similar to that used by Lekhnitskii(6). It is seen that the effect of increasing the rotational restraint is most significant at low values of R . Hence to increase the buckling load or the post buckling stiffness only a fairly small restraint on the unloaded edges is necessary. The full lines indicate the case of equal rotational restraint on both edges while the dotted lines are for the case with one edge simply supported.

Buckle length or plate geometry also has an effect on the post buckling stiffness. Fig.4 indicates the increase in E^*/E for various values of restraint coefficient on the unloaded edges. Actually the buckle length would not increase indefinitely. The plate would tend to buckle into more than one half wave length. Point C indicates the approximate position where the highly restrained plate would tend to change into the next buckle mode. The Fig. indicates that if some increase in the buckle length can be achieved there is a gain in structural efficiency in the post buckling regime.

The out of plane deflection on a number of different plates as a function of the post buckling load is indicated in Fig.5. This shows the effect of increasing the stiffness ratio E_{11}/E_{22} for a particular value of shear modulus and Poisson's ratio. As E_{11}/E_{22} is increased the deflection is reduced. In each case they are less than the value obtained for the isotropic plate. They may be considered as a series of plates with a constant stiffness in the x direction and a reducing stiffness in the y direction. This would mean that the critical stress would be reducing as the stiffness ratio increased. The effect of increasing the ratio E_{11}/G_{12} would be to reduce the deflections even further.

It should be noted that these results differ from those presented by Prabhakara & Chia (1). This may be explained in terms of the different boundary conditions on the loaded ends taken in the two papers. Since these authors assume a constant stress across the plate after buckling, there is a significant difference in the stress at the centre of the plate in the two approaches. The larger stress obtained at the centre will result in significant increases in deflection. The stress distributions in the present case will be presented later.

The deflection profile along the y axis at the central region of square simply supported plates is given in Fig.6. The basis of

the comparison in this case is a constant post buckling deflection ratio. The corresponding P/P_{cr} is around 2.

Theoretical membrane and bending stress distributions are presented later where correlation with experimental work is indicated.

Experimental Work and Correlation with Theory

The test rig details have been described by Banks (7) elsewhere. The boundary conditions in the rig correspond with those used in the analysis. Details of the fabrication of test specimens are also given. Results of tests on 12 plates are described in detail, interest being centred mainly on the ratio of ultimate load to the critical load carried by the plate.

The same rig was used in the present case to corroborate the stress distribution occurring in the plate in the post buckling regime together with the out of plane deflections. Representative results from tests on one plate only are given to indicate the correlation. The plate referred to in Figs. as Plate 2 was fabricated with glass fibres in a polyester matrix having the properties $E_{11} = 29.8 \text{ GN/m}^2$, $E_{22} = 6.30 \text{ GN/m}^2$, $G_{12} = 2.06 \text{ GN/m}^2$ and $\nu_{12} = 0.33$. A square plate was tested, appropriately strain gauged along the centre line at the crest of the buckle.

The theoretical membrane and bending stress distributions for the above square simply supported plate are given in Fig.7. The combined effect of these stresses on the compressive side of the plate are also given. Experimental results for two values of P/P_{cr} are also given. The correlation is seen to be good when the P_{cr} load is not too greatly in excess of that to cause buckling. As the load is increased the results deviate, particularly near the edges of the plate. This may be explained in terms of a change in the deflected form of the plate at loads considerably in excess of that to produce buckling. The membrane stress is seen to take the usual form for a simply supported plate.

Comparison of experimental and theoretical out of plane deflection curves are presented in Fig.8. The correlation is seen to be excellent and would certainly appear to confirm the validity of the theory. The out of plane deflection for this plate is seen to be less than any of those presented in Fig.5. This confirms the earlier conclusion that increasing the E_{11}/G_{12} ratio reduces the relative out of plane deflection.

Discussion and Conclusions

Composite panels are being increasingly applied to aircraft and

aerospace structures. The present paper gives a theoretical analysis of the behaviour of a particular class of composite construction, the orthotropic plate, under in plane loading. The post buckling behaviour is examined for elastically restrained boundary conditions on the unloaded edges together with simple supports at the loaded ends.

The results presented are based on a four term solution to the buckling problem. This gave very accurate values for the critical buckling loads when compared to exact solutions for the simply supported case. The deflections and stresses in the post buckling regime for various typical plates are presented. The effect of increasing the rotational restraint on the unloaded edges on the critical buckling load and post buckling stiffness is also given.

As expected, it was found that increasing the rotational restraint in the unloaded edges increases the buckling load together with the post buckling stiffness. The effect is most marked at low values of the coefficient of restraint. Also as the stiffness ratio E_{11}/E_{22} is increased for a constant value of G_{12} and ν_{12} the relative out of plane deflections reduce. This is most marked at low values of the modulus ratio. Decreasing the shear modulus G_{12} has the same effect. It should be noted that in both cases the critical buckling load is reduced.

Results of a limited series of experiments are also presented. The out of plane deflection readings show excellent agreement with the theory. The experimental stress distributions also show good agreement for loads not greatly in excess of buckling. As the load is increased considerably beyond that required to produce initial buckling the edge stress shows some deviation. This may be due to a change in the deflected form from that in the initially buckled plate.

Taken together with earlier results obtained by the author (7), the results here show that there is a possibility of having a considerable reserve of post buckling strength available. This obtains since the critical buckling stress for orthotropic plates is well below the ultimate tensile strength. Certainly, designing on the basis of critical buckling load alone should give a considerable factor of safety.

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Notation

A_n	Coefficients in deflection series
a, b	Panel dimensions in x and y directions respectively
D_{11}, D_{22}	Flexural rigidity of plate per unit width for bending about the y and x axes respectively, given by $D_{11} = E_{11} h^3 / 12 (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})$ and $D_{22} = E_{22} h^3 / 12 (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})$
D_{33}	Twisting rigidity of plate about x and y axes, given by $D_{33} = Gh^3 / 12$
E_{11}, E_{22}	Modulus of elasticity in the x and y directions respectively
e	Ratio of buckle half wave length to plate width
F	Airy stress function, defined in text
G_{12}	Elastic shear modulus in x - y plane
K	Elastic buckling coefficient for orthotropic plates
h	Plate thickness
u, v	In-plane displacements, of the plate middle surface, in the x and y directions respectively
w	Out-of-plane deflections of the plate
V_1, V_2, V_3	Strain energy due to bending, in-plane stresses and rotational restraint respectively.
$Y(y)$	Deflections across buckled plate
ϵ_x, ϵ_y	Membrane strains in the x and y directions respectively
γ_{xy}	Shear strain in the x - y plane
σ_{cr}	Critical buckling stress
σ_x, σ_y	Direct membrane stresses in the x and y directions respectively
τ_{xy}	Shear stress in x - y plane
ν_{12}, ν_{21}	Poisson's ratio in the x and y directions respectively
Primes	Denote differentiation in the y -direction, e.g. $F'' = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2}$

Other symbols used in the text are defined when they appear.

FIG. 1 Co-ORDINATE AXES AND SIGN CONVENTION

FIG. 2. LOAD-END DISPLACEMENT CURVES FOR SQUARE GRP. PLATE.

FIG 3. EFFECT OF ROTATIONAL RESTRAINT ON POST BUCKLING STIFFNESS AND BUCKLING LOAD

FIG 4. EFFECT OF INCREASING BUCKLE LENGTH ON POST BUCKLING STIFFNESS FOR GRP PLATE

FIG 5 TYPICAL RELATION BETWEEN LOAD AND CENTRAL DEFLECTION FOR SQUARE SIMPLY SUPPORTED PLATES

FIG 6. DEFLECTION PROFILE ALONG y AXIS

PLATE 2

$P/P_{cr} = 1.88$

$P_{cr} = 3.9 MN/m^2$

$P/P_{cr} = 2.65$

FIG 7. COMPARISON OF THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS IN SYMMETRICAL HALF OF SQUARE GRP. PLATE.

PLATE 2

FIG 8. LOAD/OUT OF PLANE DEFLECTION CURVES.